

Commission on Climate, Energy and Sustainability

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Dear Mayor Romero, City Council Members, and Manager Thomure,

The Commission on Climate, Energy, and Sustainability submits this letter alongside its report, “Distributed Capacity Procurement: A Model for Fast and Cheap Clean Energy in Tucson.”

Distributed Capacity Procurement (DCP) is a utility-led model in which TEP deploys, owns, and operates rooftop solar and battery storage at homes and businesses across Tucson. Such a model allows for **rapid deployment of clean energy that can place downward pressure on energy prices.**

The Commission continues to explore other pathways to clean energy and presents this information as another option for the Mayor and Council’s consideration. Pursuing DCP additionally dovetails well with the Energy Collaboration Agreement.

Notably, **the City and TEP have already demonstrated this model** works. The battery installation at the Donna R. Liggins Recreation Center -- utility-owned, rate-based, and co-located with solar at a City facility -- is a DCP project in everything but name. A full DCP deployment would scale up what the City and TEP have already built together.

The full report, including fiscal modeling, case studies, and implementation roadmap, is enclosed for the Mayor and Council’s review. The Commission is available to present its findings and welcomes the opportunity to discuss next steps.

Respectfully submitted,
Commission on Climate, Energy, and Sustainability
City of Tucson

On behalf of the Commission members:

Daniel Stormont (Chair), Ojas Sanghi, Garrett Weaver, Adriana Bachmann, Camila Martins-Bekat, Katherine Tyler Swaim Brown, Natalie Shepp, Joseph Rivera, Moises Gomez